

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS

Akhmedov Akmal Yusufovich

Teacher of the Department of Pedagogy, Fergana State University

Egamberdiyev Oyatillokh Alisher ugli

3rd year student of the Faculty of pedagogy and psychology of Fergana State University

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Abstract. *The urgent task today is to form a person who fully meets the requirements of the ongoing reforms in society, is competitive in the manufacturing sector, able to adapt to sharp changes, as well as effectively operates at the level of qualification requirements in the labor market. This article deals with the formation of professional competence in the training of future teachers.*

Keywords: *professional competence, communication, competence, communication.*

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ У БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ

Аннотация. *Актуальной задачей на сегодняшний день является формирование человека, полностью отвечающего требованиям проводимых в обществе реформ, конкурентоспособного в производственной сфере, способного адаптироваться к резким изменениям, а также эффективно действовать на уровне квалификационных требований на рынке труда. . В данной статье речь идет о формировании профессиональной компетентности при подготовке будущих учителей.*

Ключевые слова: *профессиональная компетентность, общение, компетенция, общение.*

INRODUCTION

The formation of the professional competence of the future teacher has a special place among the complex problems of teacher training. Especially at the current stage of reforms related to the modernization of education, the problem of adaptation to professional pedagogical activity is becoming more apparent. It enriches future teachers with practical, psychological, methodological, research types, as well as the formation of professional competence of the teacher.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Diagnosis of professional competence Important characteristics of professional formation should include diagnostic, communicative, managerial and projective training groups. The cognitive activity of the educator is determined in many respects by the complexity, dynamics, non-standardity of the objects studied, the influence of the boundaries that separate social phenomena, their search, uncertainty, which implies observation, the ability to model the inner world of the interlocutor. In this case, the features of self-regulation are characterized by the need to constantly improve their knowledge and skills, the ability to strictly coordinate their actions towards other people.

RESULTS

In the works devoted to the study of the professional competence of the educator, it is distinguished by the following types:

- special training ability

- a sufficiently high level of professional activity, the ability to design their future professional development;
- competence of social upbringing;
- mastery of joint professional activity, cooperation, as well as professional communication methods adopted in this book, social responsibility for the results of their professional career.

DISCUSSION

The future teacher is formed on the basis of professional competence, willpower, intellectual potential, emotional qualities, practical skills, interdependence of self-management abilities and individual qualities that reflect the level of socio-cultural activity of the individual.

According to the tradition formed in European countries, professional qualification is measured by the competence of the specialist, and the education system aimed at its formation - by the level of knowledge, skills and abilities.

The following are important pedagogical conditions for the training of future teachers:

- normative and educational-methodical documents that can meet modern requirements (state educational standard, standard curricula, working curricula, standard curricula, working programs, textbooks, manuals, methodical recommendations, additional special literature, visual aids, lesson plans, availability of projects, etc.);
- high level of knowledge, skills and abilities of scientific and pedagogical staff (professors, associate professors, teachers, qualified teachers, technical staff), a sufficiently developed level of professional competence and scientific potential;
- material and technical of the educational process (educational buildings, classrooms, training workshops, practical and laboratory equipment), information technology (radio, television, computers, copiers, laboratory equipment, audio, video, multimedia, simulators, film projectors, availability of slide projectors, video projectors, a set of technical means, etc.);
- creation of a socially and educationally technologically favorable environment (teachers, students, leaders and students, as well as the content, direction, unity of purpose, etc. of student interactions);
- consistent, continuous and systematic organization of organizational and educational activities.

CONCLUSIONS

Summarizing the definition and description of the concept of "professional competence of the teacher", it can be interpreted as follows: Professional competence of a teacher is one of the most important aspects of professional competence in teaching. represents their interests.

To do this, he:

- tend to manage the creative research process;
- it should be remembered that the effectiveness of creative research depends on the pedagogical, psychological and theoretical training of the teacher.

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